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INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS IN INIDA: A NEW REGIME

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Introduction

The concept of Intellectual Property is not new as Renaissance northern Italy is thought to be the cradle of the Intellectual Property system. A Venetian Law of 1474 made the first systematic attempt to protect the inventions by a form of patent, which granted an exclusive right to an individual for the first time. In the same century, the invention of movable type and the printing press by Johannes Gutenberg around 1450, contributed to the origin of the first copyright system in the world.

Towards the end of 19th century, new inventive ways of manufacture helped trigger large-scale industrialization accompanied by rapid growth of cities, expansion of railway networks, the investment of capital and a growing transoceanic trade. New ideals of industrialism, the emergence of stronger centralized governments and nationalism led many countries to establish their modern Intellectual Property laws. At this point of time, the International Intellectual Property system also started to take shape with the setting up of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property in 1883 and the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works in 1886. The premise underlying Intellectual Property throughout its history has been that the recognition and rewards associated with ownership of inventions and creative works stimulate further inventive and creative activity that, in turn, stimulates economic growth.

Over a period of time and particularly in contemporary corporate paradigm, ideas and knowledge have become increasingly important parts of trade. Most of the value of high technology products and new medicines lies in the amount of invention, innovation, research, design and testing involved. Films, music, recordings, books, computer software and on-line services are bought and sold because of the information and creativity they contain, not usually because of the plastic, metal or paper used to make them. Many products that used to be traded as low-technology goods or commodities now contain a higher proportion on invention and design in their value, for example, brand-named clothing or new varieties of plants. Therefore, creators are given the right to prevent others from using their inventions, design or other creations. These rights are known as intellectual property rights.

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The Convention establishing the World Intellectual Property Organization (1967) gives the following lists of the subject matter protected by the Intellectual Property rights:-

- Literary, artistic and scientific works
- Performances of performing artists, phonograms and broadcasts
- Inventions in all fields of human endeavor
- Scientific discoveries
- Industrial designs
- Trademarks, service marks and commercial names and designation
- Protection against unfair competition and
- “All other rights resulting from intellectual activity in the industrial, scientific, literary or artistic fields.”

With the establishments of the WTO, the importance and role of the intellectual property protection has been crystallized in the trade related Intellectual property System (TRIPS) agreement. It was negotiated at the end of the Uruguay Round of the general agreement of Tariffs and Trade (GATT) Treaty in 1994.

The TRIPS agreement and compasses, in principle, all forms of Intellectual Property and aims at harmonizing and strengthening standards of protection and providing for effective enforcement at both international and national level. It addresses applicability of general GATT principles as well as the provisions in international agreements on IP (Part I). it establishes standards for availability, scope, use (Part II), enforcement (Part III), acquisition and maintenance (Part IV) of IPR. Further more, it addresses related dispute prevention and settlement mechanisms (Part V). formal provisions are addressed in Part VI and VII of the agreement, which cover transitional and institutional arrangements, respectively. The TRIPS Agreement, which came into effect on 1st January 1995, is to date the most comprehensive multilateral agreement in Intellectual Property. The areas of Intellectual Property that it covers are :

- i. Copyright and related rights (i.e. the rights of performers, producers of sound recordings and broadcasting organization.
- ii. Trademarks including service marks.
- iii. Geographical Indication including appellations of origin.
- iv. Industrial designs
- v. Patents including protection of new varieties of plants.
- vi. The layout designs (topographies of integrated circuits).
- vii. The undisclosed information including trade secrets and test data

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY SYSTEM IN INDIA

IPR provides a secure environment for investors, scientists, artists, designers, traders etc. to foster innovation and scientific temper. This innovation often has potential to yield astronomical returns and rewards to creators and users. Obviously, original inventors shall have rights to such profits. However it is imperative that society at large should also be benefited by such outcomes. Thus, IPR regime aims to strike balance between public and private rights.

Patents are granted for 20 years on any new product or process to original creator. After expiry of 20 years such patents expire and generic industry can exploit what was once patented. When we say Indian pharmaceutical industry is world leader in generic drugs, it means that they manufacture mostly those drugs whose patents have been expired. In other words, for 20 years law guards private rights and then they make sure that innovation is thrown open to public, hence striking a balance.

Intervention of state in guarding tangible property of citizens like immovable property, cash, jewelry etc seems more obvious. These things can be enclosed in a limited space and protected. In these things title of ownership can be made clear by invoices and payments. State's law and order machineries have been protecting citizens' right to these properties from the times immemorial. However, ideas, intellect, art, programming codes and designs etc. have only recently come under definition of property. As article 300A provides right to own property to citizens, it becomes duty of state to protect intellectual property too.

If these things are to be stolen, physical custody is not required. It means that state can't prevent proliferation of an innovative idea. Hence, it shall strive to provide exclusive right to creator to exploit its creation. Even when everyone knows the idea, secret or key, all except inventor are forbidden by law to exploit it. These things can only be used after due authorization from creator or on expiry of protection.

Not everyone is in favor of this IPR protection provided by state. Some people claim that no innovation is done in isolation. They are result of incremental innovations which are on from times immemorial. So any innovation, rather than individual asset is a social asset. Further, it is argued that most new patents are result of serendipity. There is no co-relation between effort, outcomes and rewards. Notwithstanding strength of these criticisms, it should be realised that over the years IPR protections have encouraged tremendous investments and efforts in areas of applied science. We have overcome numerous challenges in various fields of medicine, communication, agriculture, communication, transport etc. As already said, knowledge knows

no boundaries. It is hence not enough to provide protection to a creation in domestic laws. In globalized world economy it is imperative that a universal protection is accorded. For this we have robust international system of treaty instruments and enforcement organizations.

VARIOUS INTERNATIONAL TREATIES

There are different subject matters of intellectual property like Patents, Copyright, Trademarks, Industrial design, Plant Varieties etc. Need for protection in these different subjects arose in different periods. These are reflected in different treaties. Agreement on TRIPS, under aegis of WTO, remains most influential, comprehensive and inclusive of all. Other treaties are covered here for background information.

There are two main bodies – World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) under UN which administers 1-7 treaties mentioned below. 8th treaty is independent of any organization. Another relevant body is World Trading Organization. 9th (or TRIPS) is administered by WTO. 10th treaty comes under UNESCO.

1. Paris Convention for Industrial Property, 1883 – Since it deals only with Industrial property, it covered only Patents and Trademarks. It was among first treaties to recognize various principles of international trade like National Treatment, Right of Priority, Common rules etc.
2. Bern convention for literary and artistic works, 1886 – It provided for copyright system. It doesn't provide for any formality to claim protection. Protection is automatically accorded to any creation, provided work is original and other conditions under the treaty are fulfilled. It means that your work, if original, is already protected. You can claim that you have copyright.
3. Madrid Agreement, 1881 – Governs the international recognition of trademarks. Made international filings easy and cheap.
4. Patent co-operation treaty, 1970 – It was earlier not possible for an entity to claim protection in different countries by single application. This was made possible as it aimed for co-operation and it was open for all parties to Paris convention.
5. Budapest Treaty of 1980 – It made possible patenting for micro-organisms. Claimant is required to deposit his invention on micro-organisms with an Authority – 'International depository of Micro-Organisms' under WIPO. He shall make all the adequate disclosures.

6. Trademark Law Treaty, 1994 – Harmonized administrative procedures and introduced ‘service marks’ in ambit of trade marks. Earlier trademarks were accorded only to goods.
7. The Hague agreement concerning the International Deposit of ‘Industrial Design’ 1925 – It created International Design Bureau of WIPO.
8. International Union for protection of new varieties of plants, 1961 – This provides breeders and farmers right to new plant varieties.
9. Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property – It is a landmark and most comprehensive treaty on Intellectual property. While earlier treaties’ subject matters were specific, TRIPS deal with 8 kinds of property rights – Patents, Trademarks, trade dress, Copyrights, Industrial Designs, Plant Varieties, Integrated Circuits and layouts, and Geographical Indication. Further, almost all countries are party to TRIP. In earlier treaties only limited countries participated. It also provides enforcement mechanism which was not available in WIPO treaties. It mandated all member countries to make their domestic laws complaint to TRIPS. India passed certain laws and amended others. India’s IPR regime now stands fully complaint to TRIPS. For E.g. India amended patent law in 2005 to provide ‘product’ patent protection. Earlier protection was available only to ‘processes’.

TRIPS was results of discussions held in Uruguay round which led to formation of WTO. This treaty is an offshoot of General Agreement on Trade in Goods (GATT). This treaty provided a robust Dispute Resolution Mechanism and stringent penal provisions under auspices of WTO.

Further, every treaty under WTO is based some principle which are –

1. National Treatment – No foreign products, once they enter domestic territories, shall be discriminated in any manner. This also applies to intellectual property. Members must accord similar treatment to foreign creations, as they do to domestic ones.
2. Most Favored Nation – If a member provides some privilege, favorable treatment or exemption to another country or group, then other members must get similar favorable treatment.
3. Right to priority treatment – If a similar patent application has been filed in two different countries, then prior applicant has right to the patent.
4. Concept of Minimum Standards – This treaty provides for minimum level of protection that every member should provide to intellectual property. Members have discretion to provide more protection than minimum standards.

5. Universal Copyright Convention, 1952 – This convention is administered by UNESCO. This exists simultaneously with Bern Convention. This treaty provides for procedural formalities for filing and recognition of copyright. As Bern convention provides for automatic route to copyright, this treaty has lost its relevance.

INITIATIVES OF GOVERNMENT OF INDIA TOWARDS PROTECTION OF IPR

1. The Government has brought out A Handbook of Copyright Law to create awareness of copyright laws amongst the stakeholders, enforcement agencies, professional users like the scientific and academic communities and members of the public.
2. National Police Academy, Hyderabad and National Academy of Customs, Excise and Narcotics conducted several training programs on copyright laws for the police and customs officers.
3. . The Department of Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India has initiated several measures in the past for strengthening the enforcement of copyrights that include constitution of a Copyright Enforcement Advisory Council (CEAC), creation of separate cells in state police headquarters, encouraging setting up of collective administration societies and organization of seminars and workshops to create greater awareness of copyright laws among the enforcement personnel and the general public.
4. Special cells for copyright enforcement have so far been set up in 23 States and Union Territories, i.e. Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Chandigarh, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Orissa, Pondicherry, Punjab, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura and West Bengal.
5. The Government also initiates a number of seminars/workshops on copyright issues. The participants in these seminars include enforcement personnel as well as representatives of industry organizations.

IPR REGIME IN INIDA

The establishment of WTO as a result of institutionalization of international framework of trade calls for harmonization of several aspects of Indian Law relating to IPR. The TRIPS agreement set minimum standards for protection of IPR rights and also set a time frame within which countries were required to make changes in their law to comply with the required degree of protection. In the view of this, India has taken action to modify and amend the warriors IP Acts in the last few years.

PATENTS ACT, 1970

After India became a signatory to the TRIPS agreement forming part of the agreement establishing the WTO for the purpose of reduction of distortion and impediments to International Trade and promotion of effective and adequate protection of IPR, the Patents Act, 1970 has been amended in the year 1995, 1999, 2002 and 2005 to meet its obligations under the TRIPS agreements. The Patents Act has been amended keeping in view the development of technological capability in India, coupled with the need for integrating the Intellectual Property system with the International practices and IP regime. The amendments were also aimed at making the act modern, harmonized and user friendly legislation to adequately protect National and public interests while simultaneously meeting India's International Obligation under the TRIPS agreement.

Subsequently, the rules under the Patent Act have also been amended and these became effective from May 2003. These rules have been further amended by Patents (amendments) Rules, 2005 w.e.f. 01.01.2005. Thus the Patent Amendments Act, 2005 is now fully in force and operative.

TRADEMARK ACT, 1999

The law of trademarks is also now modernized under the Trademarks Act of 1999. A Trademark is a special symbol of distinguishing the goods offered for sale or otherwise put on the market by one trader from those of another. In India the trademarks have been protected for over four decades as per the provisions of the Trade and Merchandise Mark Act, 1958. India became a party to the WTO at its very inception. One of the agreements in that related to the IPR. In December, 1998 India acceded to the Paris Convention.

The Trademark Bill of 1999, was passed by Parliament that received the assent of the President on 30th December 1999 as Trademarks Act 1999 thereby replacing the Trade and Merchandise Act of 1958.

THE DESIGNS ACT 2000

Design right is a *sui generis* intellectual property right in British law. There are two types of design rights: the registered design right (Registered Design Act 1949) and the unregistered design right.

Design right protects the shape of a three-dimensional design. It subsists if the design is recorded on paper, or if an article has been made according to that design. It does not subsist in designs made before the commencement of part of the 1988 Act relevant to design right. It has rules on qualification for protection by both citizenship of the designer and place of the designing.

THE GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS OF GOODS (REGISTRATION AND PROTECTION) ACT, 1999

In many countries the protection afforded to geographical indications by law is similar to the protection afforded to trademarks, and in particular, certification marks. Geographical indications law restricts the use of the GIs for the purpose of identifying a particular type of product, unless the product and/or its constituent materials and/or its fabrication method originate from a particular area and/or meet certain standards. Sometimes these laws also stipulate that the product must meet certain quality tests that are administered by an association that owns the exclusive right to license or allow the use of the indication. Although a GI is not strictly a type of trademark as it does not serve to exclusively identify a specific commercial enterprise, there are usually prohibitions against registration of a trademark which constitutes a geographical indication. In countries that do not specifically recognize GIs, regional trade associations may implement them in terms of certification marks.

COPYRIGHT ACT, 1957

Copyright is a legal right created by the law of a country that grants the creator of original work exclusive rights for its use and distribution. This is usually only for a limited time. The exclusive rights are not absolute but limited by limitations and exceptions to copyright law, including fair use. A major limitation on copyright is that copyright protects only the original expression of ideas, and not the underlying ideas themselves.

Copyright is a form of intellectual property, applicable to certain forms of creative work. Some, but not all jurisdictions require "fixing" copyrighted works in a tangible form. It is often shared among multiple authors, each of whom holds a set of rights to use or license the work, and who are commonly referred to as rights holders. These rights frequently include reproduction, control over derivative works, distribution, public performance, and moral rights such as attribution.

Copyrights are considered "territorial rights", which means that they do not extend beyond the territory of a specific jurisdiction. While many aspects of national copyright laws have been standardized through international copyright agreements, copyright laws vary by country.

Typically, the duration of a copyright spans the author's life plus 50 to 100 years (that is, copyright typically expires 50 to 100 years after the author dies, depending on the jurisdiction). Some countries require certain copyright formalities to establishing copyright, but most

recognize copyright in any completed work, without formal registration. Generally, copyright is enforced as a civil matter, though some jurisdictions do apply criminal sanctions.

THE PROTECTION OF PLANT VARIETIES AND FARMERS' RIGHTS ACTS 2001

The Protection of Plant Variety and Farmers Right Act, 2001 (PPVFR Act) is an Act of the Parliament of India that was enacted to provide for the establishment of an effective system for protection of plant varieties, the rights of farmers and plant breeders, and to encourage the development and cultivation of new varieties of plants. This act received the assent of the President of India on the October 30, 2001.

The PPV&FR Act, 2001 was enacted to grant intellectual property rights to plant breeders, researchers and farmers who have developed any new or extant plant varieties. The Intellectual Property Right granted under PPV&FR Act, 2001 is a dual right – one is for the variety and the other is for the denomination assigned to it by the breeder. The rights granted under this Act are heritable and assignable and only registration of a plant variety confers the right.

THE SEMI CONDUCTOR INTEGRATED CIRCUITS LAYOUT DESIGN, 2002

Layout designs (topographies) of integrated circuits are a field in the protection of intellectual property. In United States intellectual property law, a "mask work" is a two or three-dimensional layout or topography of an integrated circuit (IC or "chip"), i.e. the arrangement on a chip of semiconductor devices such as transistors and passive electronic components such as resistors and interconnections. The layout is called a *mask* work because, in photolithographic processes, the multiple etched layers within actual ICs are each created using a mask, called the photo mask, to permit or block the light at specific locations, sometimes for hundreds of chips on a wafer simultaneously.

TRADE SECRETS

The precise language by which a trade secret is defined varies by jurisdiction (as do the particular types of information that are subject to trade secret protection). However, there are three factors that, although subject to differing interpretations, are common to all such definitions: a trade secret is information that:

- Is not generally known to the public;

- Confers some sort of economic benefit on its holder (where this benefit must derive *specifically* from its not being publicly known, not just from the value of the information itself.
- Is the subject of reasonable efforts to maintain its secrecy.

CONCLUSION

Intellectual Property protection is the key factor for economic growth and advancement in the high technology sector. There are good for business, benefit the public at large and act as catalysts for technical progress. For India one among the developing countries have miles to go, as we have a vulnerable collection of traditional, oral, folklore, customary, agricultural, traditional medication like Ayurveda etc. and besides not having much wealth and infrastructure, lack of awareness of IPRs among all strata's of people, is a major setback to a developing country like India. Today the aggressive and targeted patenting is the need of the hour. Though many experts have given their own definitions and ideas but literary IPR refers to creations of the mind, inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names, images and designs used in commerce. IPR is divided into two categories- Industrial Property, which includes inventions, trademarks, industrial designs and geographic indications of source and Copyright which includes literary and artistic works such as novels, poems and plays, films, musical works, artistic works.

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